

**Software chosen for
bioinformatics analysis**

**JRP7 - ListAdapt - FBZ2 - 1st
Call**

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Responsible Partner: ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Genomics and statistical methods used in WP4

1. Preparing input data for comparative genomics analysis

The different tasks of WP4 rely on WGS data. The internal workflow (ARTwork) of ANSES (Durimel et al., 2018) was used to prepare the input data. The various tools integrated in this analysis procedure as well as the associated parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Tools used for producing Lm assemblies (steps 1 to 4) and for in silico mlst determination

Step	Tools	Version		Reference
1 Read normalization	bbtools	36.14	bbnorm : mindepth = -1 maxdepth = 1 prefilter = t tossbadreads = t bbmap : covbinsize = 1000 k=13 nodisk	https://jgi.doe.gov/data-and-tools/bbtools/bb-tools-user-guide/
2 Read quality checking	fastqc	0.11.5	-q	Andrews (2010)
3 Read curation	Trimmomatic	0.33	PE -phred33 TRAILING:20 MINLEN:50	Bolger et al. (2014)
4 Assemblies preparation	Spades	3.9.1	--carefull	Bankevitch et al. (2012)
5 7 MLST characterization	mlst	2.6	--quiet	https://github.com/tseemann/mlst https://pubmlst.org/

The first step implemented in ARTwork is the normalization of reads. The threshold set to initiate the complete analysis is 30x. If the depth is greater than 100x, the reads are then normalized to 100x in order to limit the calculation time. The reads covered between 30x and 100x are not modified. The second step is the quality control of the reads. The third step cleans reads by removing contaminant sequences or poor quality sequences to produce a more relevant assembly. The adapter sequences used for sequencing, portions of reads having a phred score less than 20 and reads smaller than 50 base pairs are then deleted. After cleaning reads, these are used for the de novo assembly of the genome

The assemblies are used for the prediction of a standard sequence (ST) by an in silico MLST tool. Once the ST is identified, it is used to predict the clonal complex (CC).

2. Diversity characterization in the different environments

The diversity characterization of *L. monocytogenes* in the different compartments will be characterized by three different methods.

Simpson's diversity index: was used to obtain an estimate of the diversity of strains by source (Simpson, 1949). This was performed at the 7 and 30 locus MLST and rMLST only, because higher resolution leads to practically all genomes being represented by a different type and so does not produce useful results. Simpson's diversity is given by:

$$Diversity\ Index = 1 - \sum_{All\ STs} (f_i)^2$$

where f_i is the relative frequency of type i in a specific source. A value of 0 of the diversity index indicates that all strains are the same and a value of 1 indicates that they are all different (maximum diversity).

Rarefaction: The extent to which the isolates from sources had sampled the maximum number of genotypes was characterised using rarefaction. Rarefaction is a data re-sampling technique that indicates whether all of the genotypes have been sampled which results in the curve reaching a plateau, or if the curve is still increasing there are still more genotypes in the population to be sampled (Heck et al., 1975).

Nei's Genetic distance: Standardized genetic distances (d_1) between pairs of sources was determined using the method of Nei (Nei, 1975) and applied to genetic MLST locus and SNP data by the method of Manly (Manly, 2007). Briefly, for N_{loci} the distance is calculated as

$$d_{1ij} = \frac{1}{N_{loci}} \sum_{All\ loci} 0.5 \left(\sum_{All\ alleles} |p_i - q_j| \right)$$

where p_i and q_j are the frequencies of the alleles (or SNPs) at each locus in source i and j , respectively. A Nei's value of 0 indicates that the populations are identical whilst a value of 1 indicates that the two populations have no genotypes in common.

3. Tools for GWAS

Many possibilities are nowadays accessible to study the association between geno- and phenotypes at the genomic scale. These possibilities rely upon advanced statistical approaches called Genome Wide Association Studies (GWAS). This approach is based on a simple principle: a genome-wide set of genetic variants in different individuals is statistically observed to see if any variant is associated with a trait. The phenotypic traits and the genomic sequences of a strain collection are therefore necessary to assess genetic variant candidates explaining the phenotypic trait of interest. Therefore, it is statistically tested if some genetic elements are more common in strains presenting the specific trait than in those that do not (Falush, 2016). GWAS can be made at different genomic levels. Usually, genomes are broken down into core and accessory genome. Then, variants such as SNPs, small indels and also k-mers (i.e. a word of DNA that is k long) are explored in the core genome are (Earle et al., 2016; Jaillard et al., 2018; Sheppard et al., 2013), whereas, the differences in presence/absence of genes are

searched in the accessory genome (e.g. through the tool Scoary developed by (Brynildsrud et al., 2016)).

For performing the GWAS related to WP3, Listadapt partners have identified the following tools (Table 2). The Listadapt group focus in choice on a tool for accessory genomes (Scoary), one based on kmer (pySEER) and one adapted for continuous phenotypes (TreeWAS).

Table 2: Bioinformatics tools for GWAS (in red the tools to be used in LISTADAPT).

Names	Genome level	Location	phenotype	approach	Publication
Roary/Scoary	Genes	Accessory	Discrete	Accounting for population stratification	(Brynildsrud et al., 2016; Page et al., 2015)
Piggy/Scoary	Intergenic regions	Pan-genome	Discrete		(Brynildsrud et al., 2016; Thorpe et al., 2017)
DBGWAS	Unitigs	Pan-Genome	Discrete	LMM (Bugwas from Earle et al., 2016)	(Jaillard et al., 2018)
treeWAS	SNPs and Genes	Pan-Genome	Discrete and continuous	Phylogenomic tree based	(Collins and Didelot, 2018)
Neptune	k-mers	Pan-Genome	Discrete		(Marinier et al., 2017)
SEER/pySEER	k-mers/unitigs	Pan-Genome	Discrete	Correction for clonal population structure	(Lees et al., 2018)
Kover	k-mers	Pan-Genome	Discrete	No correction for population structure	(Drouin et al., 2016)
Earle pipeline	SNP, k-mers,	Core-Genome Pan-genome	Discrete	LMM	(Earle et al., 2016)

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